

22NRM03 MetHyTrucks

D2 - Good practice guide for hydrogen venting during heavy duty sampling exercises, including examples of risk assessments

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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Glossary

ATEX:	explosive atmosphere
EN:	European normalisation
FCEV:	Fuel cell electrical vehicle
HD:	Heavy duty
HRS:	Hydrogen Refuelling Station
IEC:	
ISO:	International standard organisation
LD:	Light duty
SAE:	Society of automotive engineers
TC:	Technical committee

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1 Summary

The deliverable is a good practice guide for hydrogen venting during heavy duty sampling exercises. It discusses the design and design parameters for vents as well as information about ATEX zoning. It also summarizes the steps needed to prepare for a sampling event including what must be done beforehand (training, risk assessment, agreements), during (installation, preparatory steps, sampling and venting) and after (disassembly and storage/transport of the cylinders). Finally, at the end of the report, some examples of risk assessments (those have been performed for activities in MetHyTrucks) are given.

2 Introduction

Hydrogen can significantly contribute to reducing emissions from the transportation sector as it is particularly well suited as a fuel for long-haul heavy-duty (HD) vehicles. A recent report from Hydrogen Europe [1] gauged industry's commitments and predictions for the development of hydrogen in the whole transport sector and highlighted a certain degree of confidence that hydrogen-based technologies will scale up and be widely used in all applications and market segments if the proper preconditions are met. To facilitate the uptake of hydrogen as a fuel for HD vehicles, the hydrogen dispensed needs to be analysed and its purity complies to the requirements set in the relevant standards such as ISO 14687 [2], EN 17124 [3], and SAE J2719:202003 [4]. The quality of the hydrogen is controlled continuously or after spot sampling and transport to a laboratory for offline analysis [5] [6]. To do so, sampling devices are used to collect in adequate cylinders, a sample of the hydrogen dispensed.

The project MetHyTrucks has adapted existing, and developed new, sampling systems for HD applications to collect representative samples [7]. A key aspect of sampling at HRS especially HD is the safety of staff, installation and end users. Hydrogen safety, particularly venting, is critical in preventing incidents related to pressure build-up, leaks, and hydrogen accumulation in unintended spaces. Following the trials of sampling systems for HD applications [7], it was important to share knowledge on key safety elements such as safe venting and risk assessment. When these devices (or any other sampling devices) are implemented at an HRS, they may need to be purged several times with given volumes of hydrogen or at various locations of the sampling system. The purging requirement may be related to cleaning or conditioning the sampling system (i.e., previous activities, sampling or presence of air or inert gases) or to ensure representative sample of the HRS is obtained (i.e., venting allows to replace gas close to the sampling point and not considered representative of the process). Therefore, an important aspect to consider is how to safely perform hydrogen venting at an HRS during a sampling event (e.g. ATEX zoning, flow, pressure, height, authorisation). Despite sampling at LD-HRS being realised for many years, safe venting during sampling event is exacerbated at heavy duty refuelling stations due to high flowrates and the requirement to minimise downtime (i.e., station availability target for end-users). Furthermore, the initiative of ISO TC 197 to standardise sampling at HRS emphasises that safety is a key element for the standardisation document ISO 19880-9 [8].

The deliverable is a good practice guide for hydrogen venting during heavy duty sampling based on the project experience. The deliverable shares some knowledge on risk assessment and examples from the MetHyTrucks project thanks to the project realisation of several sampling campaigns at various site with diverse equipment and discussion on the realisation of risk assessment and the methodology.

3 General aspects of venting

Vent systems are used to safely release hydrogen during normal and abnormal events (as a sampling event) to reduce the risk and effects of fire, asphyxiation, and fume on people, equipment, and the environment [9].

The design and design parameters (as example, vent diameter) must take into account the properties of hydrogen (for instance highly flammable, prone to leaks due to its small molecular size, less dense than air), the operations and process flow parameters (including maximal pressure, peak flow, maximum or minimum temperature). Typical equipment of a vent system can include pressure relief devices, purge and vent valves, bleed valves, exhaust stacks [9].

The following aspects need to be considered when designing a venting system [9]:

- Pressure rating: it is a best practice to design the pressure rating of the piping at the highest rated pressure entering the vent systems;

- Risk for plugging/blocking of the vent: the system shall be designed to avoid freezing (for example due to introduction of moisture (incl. weather protection, rain...) or any obstruction);
- Correct supports: especially for vent stacks, supports should withstand reaction forces (especially from pressure safety relief valve activating), local wind, and shall be designed for vent system expansion/contraction due to temperature changes;
- Temperature rating: risk for piping expansion/contraction due to temperature changes, correct temperature rating for joints or vent system;
- Risk for air ingress back down the vent: it should be eliminated;
- Flow capacity and size of the vent system: designed for the maximum peak flow at the operating pressure;
- Eventual interaction between flow streams (for example if sampling devices are flushed with nitrogen);
- Vent stack termination and release flow; vent stacks are used to move hydrogen away from ground level; they therefore should be designed to direct the flow of hydrogen vertical upward or angled outlet and to minimize reaction forces at the top of the vent stack. Several documents can be used as references for the vent stack design [2] [3];
- Other aspects to consider to minimise risk are:
 - flaring (only for steady flow),
 - grounding (to minimize ignition sources),
 - mufflers or silencers (based on noise level in venting condition especially with high flow).
- Deployment: vent systems should be easy to deploy, and shall not require complex adjustments at the refuelling station
 - Most sampling systems use mobile venting systems with several meters of flexible hose to accommodate the variability of HRS perimeters,
 - The use of HRS venting lines could be an alternative to simplify and improve safety of sampling systems however it would require harmonisation of the venting point access across the industry and a mechanism to access it especially on unmanned sites.

4 Venting requirements in the sampling procedure

Each sampling exercise needs to be carefully planned, and risk assessments need to be conducted. The steps to conduct a sampling exercise has to be documented in a sampling procedure. Venting requirements should be included in the sampling procedure. A good example is the sampling procedure developed by ZBT which include the following steps (Shell PtW system)

- Organization of the sampling at the HRS (including permission of the operator, creation of a security zone);
- Installation of the system and connection to all belonging parts (vent, sample cylinder, FCEV, dispenser, grounding);
- Purging of the system with hydrogen from the dispenser and leak test of the sampling assembly while the system is pressurized;
- Purging of the system with hydrogen from the sample cylinder if necessary;
- Filling the cylinder to final pressure of 80 bar with hydrogen from the dispenser;
- Releasing the pressure inside the system with the mobile vent;
- Dismounting of the system and all belonging parts.

The requirements for venting differ upon the design of the sampling systems. Therefore, hydrogen sampling systems usually have their own venting strategies (e.g., portable vent) which are developed specifically for each device. For example, some devices require a purge, other are designed to function without. Some systems use the vent of the HRS while others need a venting stack. The design and parameters consider the properties of hydrogen such as its flammability, and the fact that it is prone to leaks.

5 Guidelines for a safe venting during and after a sampling operation at HRS

5.1 Design of the venting stack

5.1.1 Appropriate venting stack height

The definition of the ATEX zoning area provides requirements for the venting stack height. The Figure 1 defines a height where the venting stack should be installed. From the field experiments, it is recommended to increase the height of the exhaust to avoid any potential hydrogen going toward the ground due to the wind. From the experience gathered during previous project, it is recommended to set up the exhaust at least at 3 meters height, 4 meters height being a reference value.

5.1.2 Exhaust diameter

The exhaust diameter is also an important parameter since it drives the acoustic radiation (see Lighthill), the jet velocity and the height of the release. An appropriate balance should be determined to avoid too much noise for the surrounding areas without being too much influenced by the wind velocity. The wind velocity should be of the same order of magnitude than the hydrogen exhaust to avoid any unexpected hydrogen concentration towards the ground. It should also be compliant with the rest of the system to avoid creating back pressure.

5.1.3 Exhaust shape

The exhaust shape plays also an important role in the noise radiation and for the hydrogen jet development. It is recommended to have a top directed hydrogen jet (which is less submitted to the wind condition and the potential migration of hydrogen towards the operators and the ground).

5.2 Example of venting systems

The venting systems used in the MetHyTrucks project can be used as example of venting systems and are described in detail in the report A1.5.1 [10] and summarized in the report A1.5.2 [11] which are available on the website of MetHyTrucks (www.ri.se/en/methytrucks)

5.3 ATEX zoning: general considerations

ATEX zones are defined by the European Directive 1999/92/EC [12] and are used to classify work areas based on their level of explosion risk. The delimitation of an ATEX zone is based on a risk assessment that determines the likelihood of an explosive atmosphere forming in a given area. This assessment takes into account various factors such as the frequency and duration of the presence of explosive substances, ventilation, and potential sources of ignition. Once the risk zones have been identified, they must be clearly delimited. Delimitation methods may vary depending on circumstances, but here are some common options:

- **Ground Marking:** Zones can be delineated by ground markings in different colors for each zone, enhancing boundary identification.
- **Signs and labels:** it can be used to indicate the presence of ATEX zones and inform about specific risks.
- **Physical Barriers:** it can be used to separate risk zones from areas where explosion risks are lower.

- **Use of Specific Equipment:** Equipment such as lights, fans, and motors can be designed for specific use in ATEX zones. It's essential to note that the delimitation of ATEX zones must be regularly reassessed and updated based on changes in working conditions.

An area is considered ATEX as soon as it is used to store or handle flammable materials. The degree of danger of an ATEX area is evaluated based on the quantity and nature of these materials. The higher the level, the greater the risks, and the stricter the regulations.

The ATEX regulations are defined by two European directives:

- Directive 2014/34/UE (ATEX 95), concerning equipment used in ATEX areas;
- and Directive 1999/92/CE (ATEX 137), concerning the safety of workers in an ATEX area.

These directives require employers to control the risks of explosion on their site, just like other occupational risks. The goal is to ensure the safety and improve the health of individuals exposed to ATEX risks. There are three types of zones defined by the IEC (1986), by the Ministry of Labor (1988) and by the Ministry of Industry (1991). This classification is refined in the ATEX directive, which no longer speaks of zones but of categories of devices, depending on the probability of the formation of an explosive mixture, and two different applications depending on the nature of the mixture (gas or dust).

- **Permanent risk:** The explosive mixture is present at all times,
- **Frequent risk:** An explosive mixture of gases or vapors is likely to form during normal operation of the installation,
- **Occasional risk:** An explosive mixture can only appear in the event of abnormal operation of the installation.

The ATEX zone can be summarized into the Table 1 below:

	Zone	Material category
Gas	0: Permanent presence	1G
	1: Occasional presence	2G or 1G
	2: Rare presence	3G, 2G or 1G
Dust	0: Permanent presence	1G
	1: Occasional presence	2G or 1G
	2: Rare presence	3G, 2G or 1G

Table 1. Classification of the ATEX zoning

5.4 ATEX zoning: best practice during sampling exercise

During a sampling exercise at an HRS, the ATEX zoning should be limited to the sampling system itself (due to the medium-pressure cone and thread fittings assembly or double ferrule system, piping, valves) and the venting stack. It is commonly accepted and demonstrated that the sampling unit is rated category 2 (rare presence) whereas the venting stack is rated category 1 (occasional presence).

The cone and thread fittings or double ferrule system assembly are known to be correctly designed for tightness. The ATEX area surrounding the sampling system should be limited to around 1 meter (depending on the maximum internal pressure).

At the venting stack exhaust, the size of the ATEX area is larger. Area is at least 1 meter for ZONE 1 and up to 10 meters (for 160 bar) for ZONE 2 are usually used. The determination of the safe distance should be determined using modelling and scenarios. Several tools are available to make such calculation (i.e., elab [13]).

From a general point of view, it is recommended to properly establish a zone with fencing or tape at the vicinity of the sampling system and the venting stack.

Figure 1. ATEX zoning around the exhaust of the venting stack from the side(left), and the front (right)

6 Risk assessments

Hydrogen poses risks of fire, explosion, overpressure, and cold burns, necessitating specialized safety measures beyond those for gasoline/diesel. Standard procedures exist for routine fuelling, but specific assessments for non-standard tasks like sampling require dedicated risk evaluation (hazard identification, risk evaluation, mitigation, documentation) to protect staff and users, given hydrogen's unique risks (flammability, explosion) diverging from typical fuels.

All operators working with sampling activities should be responsible for conducting health & safety risk assessments for every step of the sampling at HRS.

The HRS operators should support sampling operators by providing a brief knowledge of hydrogen refuelling system including the site area, the refuelling system, the emergency stop push button at the dispenser, emergency response team, first aiders.

The lab managers or Health & Safety officers should review and provide feedback to the sampling operators on the sampling risk assessment and finalise an agreed version.

The approved sampling risk assessment shall be sent to HRS operators in advance. HRS operators need to prepare an onsite risk assessment (i.e., Job Hazard Analysis, work permit) based on the given sampling risk assessment.

At any moment, all operators should be able to stop safely the work if they feel unsafe situation may occur.

6.1 Methodology

MetHyTrucks report A1.5.3 [14] details the steps recommended to perform a safe sampling. The information is briefly summarized here.

Before any exercise can be organised, it is crucial to ensure that all equipment brought onsite for an exercise event is safety compliant which involves checks for proper installation, maintenance, functioning safety features, clear user instructions, and compliance with relevant regulations.

Beforehand, all operators need to be properly trained. The training needs to be repeated over time to ensure staff are up to date with the most recent standards and requirements. Roles and responsibilities need to be clearly defined. It is important the note that requirements may differ from country to country where some specific documentation may be required. Examples of documentation are the Job Hazard Analysis (JHA) which breaks down tasks to find hazards and controls; the Permit To Work (PTW) which is a formal authorization for high-risk activities, linking to the JHA; and a Work Clearance Form (WCF) which often serves as the physical form for the PTW/JHA, documenting authorization, controls, and clearance for specific tasks, ensuring communication and control for non-routine work.

Then a risk assessment must be performed. The levels of risk are identified for the sampling activity preferably using a quantitative risk matrix. It uses numerical data to assess the risk through plotting likelihood (e.g., 1-5) versus impact (e.g., 1-5) on a grid to generate a risk score (likelihood x impact). The score helps prioritize mitigation of high-scoring risks (i.e., process changes, training, equipment) to reduce likelihood or impact.

It is also important to ensure that all entities and participants agree as sampling risk assessment is added on the HRS risk assessment.

Finally, all the steps done during and after the sampling event must be safely conducted:

- 1) Preparing the sampling area (cordoning off the work area);
- 2) Using appropriate personal protective equipment;
- 3) Safe installation of the sampling equipment (earthing, positing cylinders and sampling systems);
- 4) Sampling exercise including preparatory steps (flushing with or without venting), sampling, system venting;
- 5) Safe disassembly (including depressurising the system);
- 6) Storing safely the cylinders filled with hydrogen before transportation;
- 7) Transporting the cylinders to the analysis laboratory in accordance with local and international regulation (i.e., IATA, ADR requires dangerous goods note, material safety data sheet, specific carrier’s requirements).

6.2 Examples of onsite risk assessment

Risk assessment depends on the type of sampling event. The following examples are taken from MetHyTrucks report A1.5.3. Table 1 shows an example of risk assessment for gas sampling using the quantitative approach. Table 2 shows an example of onsite risk assessment for sampling/flow metering. Table 3 shows an example of onsite risk assessment for parallel sampling. Table 4 shows an example of onsite risk assessment for direct sampling.

Step 1		Step 2	Step 3			Step 4	Step 5		
Ref No	Specific Task / Activity Steps	Identify Potential Hazards	Risk Ranking			Risk Control Measures Hierarchy of Control – Elimination, Substitution, Isolation, Engineering, Administration, Personal Protection. Additional information can be attached.	Residual Risk		
			Likelihood	Severity	Risk Rating Likelihood x Severity		Likelihood	Severity	Risk Rating Likelihood x Severity
Preparation	Documentation verification	Use of instrument not compliant with customer site or UK regulation	2	3	6	Administration – The risk assessment is sent to the customer site owner. Email from customer agreeing with the risk assessment and mitigation recorded by email Verification that the system is under written scheme of examination or equivalent and fit for use	1	3	3

Initial step	Sampling cylinder preparation	<p>Falling cylinders</p> <p>Risk / Consequence: Injury (not fatal) to operative</p> <p>To whom: Staff present during sampling event, Security</p>	2	3	6	<p>Administration – staff trained on manual handling</p> <p>Personal protection – wearing safety glasses, gloves to help with gripping cylinders, anti-static steel-toe boots and personal alarms</p> <p>Engineering: cylinder need to have valve shrink wrap, closed and capped at the arrival on the site.</p>	1	3	3
Initial step	secure the sampling area	<p>Vehicle accident</p> <p>Risk / Consequence: Injury (not fatal) to operative</p> <p>To whom: Staff present during sampling event, Security</p>	2	3	6	<p>Marking the area – traffic cones, high vis jacket for staff, activity perform during day light</p> <p>Administration risk assessment provided to site staff and site risk assessment provided to staff</p>	1	3	3
Step 1-5	Installation of the sample taking bottle and vent	<p>Falling cylinders or falling vent</p> <p>Risk / Consequence: Injury (not fatal) to operative</p> <p>To whom: Staff present during sampling event, Security</p>	2	3	6	<p>Administration – staff trained on manual handling</p> <p>Personal protection – wearing safety glasses, gloves to help with gripping cylinders, anti-static steel-toe boots and personal alarms</p> <p>Engineering: weather will be checked, sandbag or equivalent added to stabilise vent system</p>	1	3	3
Step 1-5	removing the metal valve protective cap	<p>Falling cylinders</p> <p>Risk / Consequence: Injury (not fatal) to operative</p> <p>To whom: Staff present during sampling event, Security</p>	2	3	6	<p>Administration – staff trained on manual handling</p> <p>Personal protection – wearing safety glasses, gloves to help with gripping cylinders, anti-static steel-toe boots and personal alarms</p>	1	3	3
Step 1-5	Attach the pressure reducer to the cylinder	<p>Falling cylinders</p> <p>Risk / Consequence: Injury (not fatal) to operative</p> <p>To whom: Staff present during sampling event, Security</p>	2	3	6	<p>Administration – staff trained on manual handling</p> <p>Verify that pressure reducer is in date (written scheme of examination)</p> <p>Regulator is fixed pressure (max 140 bar)</p> <p>PRV present at 175 bar</p> <p>Personal protection – wearing safety glasses, gloves to help with gripping cylinders, anti-static steel-toe boots and personal alarms</p>	1	3	3
Step 1-5	Connecting the high-pressure hose to the pressure reducer	<p>Falling cylinders</p> <p>Risk / Consequence: Injury (not fatal) to operative</p> <p>To whom: Staff present during sampling event, Security</p>	2	3	6	<p>Administration – staff trained on manual handling</p> <p>Personal protection – wearing safety glasses, gloves to help with gripping cylinders, anti-static steel-toe boots and personal alarms</p> <p>Engineering – pressure regulator reducing pressure below 120 bar / pressure at the sampling point is 230 bar</p>	1	3	3

Step 10	System leak checking using HRS	<p>Hydrogen leak from equipment (located between the dispenser and the cylinder)</p> <p>Risk / consequence: Ignition causing fire or explosion</p> <p>To whom: Staff present during sampling event, Security</p>	3	5	<p>15</p> <p>Prevention of damage / wear: procedure includes visual inspection of customer sampling point and hose, prior to refuelling, checking for damaged components / debris.</p> <p>Prevention / minimisation of leak uses SAE J2600 compliant receptacle. Positive engagement required for gas flow. Leak checking is realised with site pressure reduced at 20 pressure. Filling and pressure controlled by customer operative present on site. Flow and pressure are minimised. leak check carried out by trained staff. Verify training done (email by senior staff or internal record) Anything above a minor leak will be audible and fuelling can be halted using the emergency stop push button at the dispenser. Therefore one staff is next to the emergency stop button while the other is working. staff carry portable hydrogen alarms and hydrogen leak detector to monitor the system and identify leak at early stage. If any leak observed by portable alarms or leak detector, the sampling must be halted using the emergency stop push button at the dispenser. Verify leak detector and alarm operating correctly before use (i.e., powers up, enough battery and in date calibration)</p> <p>Prevention of ignition Outdoor refuelling only to ensure adequate ventilation. Area around dispenser is zone 2, with appropriate electrical equipment used. No vehicle present next to the refueller and power electronics turned off during refuelling. It will be ensured that any non-ATEX equipment will be at least 1.5 metres away from the receptacle/nozzle connection and other potential leak points in the sampling system, and a hydrogen sensor will be used during fuelling.</p> <p>Protection of personnel All non-approved personnel outside 5m separation distance during refuelling – Traffic cones are implemented to stop public</p>	1	5	5
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						<p>cars entering in the 5 meters area, sampling area on the station not available for public use during operations.</p> <p>Personnel not directly involved in the sampling to be at least 5m away from the dispenser during sampling.</p> <p>E-stop push buttons that would stop the flow of hydrogen to the dispenser nozzle should be identified by staff. One staff should be ready to push the e-stop button should any incidents happen.</p> <p>Personal protection – wearing safety glasses, gloves to help with gripping cylinders, anti-static steel-toe boots and personal alarms, high vis jacket for staff, activity perform during day light and ear protection to be worn.</p>			
Step 11	Cylinder purging	<p>Hydrogen controlled release from the pressure reducer pressure relief valve</p> <p>Release of a large volume of H₂ >5L</p> <p>Risk / Consequence: Injury (potentially fatal) to operative To whom: Staff present during sampling event, Security</p>	3	5	15	<p>Prevention / minimisation of hydrogen release staff in charge of the control release should follow all the prevention of ignition requirement.</p> <p>The staff will be wearing anti-static clothing, gloves, wear safety glasses and ear protection.</p> <p>The actions of controlled release will be performed after verifying that the station has stopped the fill and is in standby mode or isolated from the sampling system. The controlled release will be performed by the trained staff using the system venting flow path and a safe vent implemented on site with approval of the site owner. The venting will be realised in safe venting condition Ensure hydrogen relief point is safe and agreed with site owner / covered by customer/partner's risk assessment</p> <p>If there are any concerns work must stop immediately</p> <p>See Prevention of ignition and Protection of Personnel in previous section</p>	1	5	5

<p>Step 12</p>	<p>Sample taking - 1/3</p>	<p>Hydrogen leak from HYDRASUN equipment located between the dispenser and the HRS</p> <p>Risk / consequence: Ignition causing fire or explosion</p> <p>To whom: Staff present during sampling event, Security</p>	<p>3</p>	<p>5</p>	<p>15</p>	<p>Follow the risk control measures of previous section</p> <p>Prevention / minimisation of hydrogen release staff in charge of the sampling should follow all the prevention of ignition requirement.</p> <p>The staff will be wearing anti-static clothing, gloves, wear safety glasses and ear protection.</p> <p>The actions sampling will be performed sequentially and include leak checking at all pressure level.</p> <p>A staff and the customer operator will be close to emergency stop to stop the hydrogen in case of any events.</p> <p>Ensure hydrogen relief point is safe and agreed with site owner / covered by customer/partner's risk assessment</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>5</p>	<p>5</p>
<p>Step 12</p>	<p>Sample taking – 2 / 3</p>	<p>Sampling vessels falling over during the filling,</p> <p>Risk / consequence: Release of hydrogen, Ignition causing fire or explosion cylinder becoming a projectile or flailing hose if disconnected Injury (potentially fatal) to operative</p> <p>To whom: Staff present during sampling event, Security</p>	<p>2</p>	<p>5</p>	<p>10</p>	<p>Minimisation of the risk of cylinder falling: Vessels strapped into cylinder stand to prevent them from falling over or use of strapped belt onto a solid point (if cylinder stand/trolley are not available).</p> <p>Sample cylinder has a collar that would protect the valve connection to minimise the likelihood of it shearing off.</p> <p>Fill carried out by trained staff.</p> <p>Anything above a minor leak will be audible and fuelling can be halted using the emergency stop push button at the dispenser.</p> <p>Limited presence of staff around the cylinder to limit to risk of cylinder falling over.</p> <p>See Prevention of ignition and Protection of Personnel in 4.2.22</p> <p>In addition: Safety footwear to be worn</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>5</p>	<p>5</p>

Step 12	Sample taking - 3/3	<p>Over-pressurisation of the sampling vessels / system</p> <p>Risk consequence: Vessel rupture, ignition causing fire or explosion</p> <p>Component failure, ignition causing fire or explosion</p> <p>Opening of the pressure release valve, leading to a release of hydrogen in the vicinity of the dispenser.</p> <p>To whom: Staff present during sampling event, Security</p>	2	5	10	<p>Prevention / minimisation of leak: Maximum fill pressure limited by system operator and system regulator to 100 bar. This is less than the maximum operating pressure permitted for the sampling equipment (supplied with the pressure regulator), and the sample cylinder (rated to 230 bar) Pressure gauge supplied downstream of the system pressure regulator to enable monitoring of the cylinder pressure. If a pressure greater than 140 bar is seen on the pressure gauge, the fuelling can be halted using the emergency stop push button at the dispenser. A pressure relief valve is included as part of the instrument, set at 175 bar. See Prevention of ignition and Protection of Personnel above</p>	1	5	5
Step 13	End of the sample taking process (1/2)	<p>Sampling vessels falling over during the filling,</p> <p>Risk / consequence: Release of hydrogen, Ignition causing fire or explosion cylinder becoming a projectile or flailing hose if disconnected Injury (potentially fatal) to operative</p> <p>To whom: Staff present during sampling event, Security</p>	2	5	10	<p>Minimisation of the risk of cylinder falling: staff closing the cylinder should be close to the cylinder during the whole refuelling. Limited movement of the staff avoid risk of cylinder fall. Follow the risk control measures of 4.2.10 (3)</p>	1	5	5
Step 13	Relief of hydrogen from pressure reducer (2/2)	<p>Hydrogen control release from the pressure reducer pressure relief valve</p> <p>Creation of an explosive atmosphere</p> <p>Risk / Consequence: Injury (potentially fatal) to operative To whom: Staff present during sampling event, Security</p>	3	5	15	<p>Follow the risk control measures of step 4</p>	1	5	5
Step 13	Deactivating the filling coupling and removal of the sampling kit	<p>Hurt with heavy equipment</p>	2	3	6	<p>Wear protective steel cap shoes, gloves and use of forklift to avoid lifting heavy equipment</p>	1	3	3

Step 14	Storage, labelling and shipment of the gas sampling cylinder	<p>Cylinder leaks or improperly stored or transported</p> <p>Risk / consequence: Release of hydrogen, Ignition causing fire or explosion cylinder becoming a projectile or flailing hose if disconnected Injury (potentially fatal) to operative</p> <p>To whom: Staff present during sampling event, Security</p>	2	5	10	<p>Minimisation of the risk of cylinder leaks: The gas cylinders are TPED marked and safe for transport according to EU regulations. Authorised transport company will be able to transport the cylinder Storage will be agreed beforehand with the HRS operator and the transport company to ensure safe storage according to local regulations During transport the gas cylinder is closed and cylinder cap attached.</p> <p>Follow the risk control measures of 4.2.10 (3)</p>	1	5	5
Highest Remaining Residual Risk							5		

Table 1. Risk assessment for gas sampling using the quantitative approach.

JHA - Job Hazard Analysis / Onsite risk assessment				Page 1/1	
The Predetermined JHA must be reviewed for the work that will occur EACH DAY that the permit is open! - Before and during work and in the event of changes: Observe the LMRA (Last Minute Risk Assessment)!					
Company:	JHA-No.:	Date:	Site-address and -No.:		
To be executed task (s):					
Creator of JHA:					
Activities with high / medium risk (definition: see BBS activity table)			Special works:	More or other forms:	
hot work <input type="checkbox"/> H <input type="checkbox"/> M	work in tight spaces <input type="checkbox"/> H <input type="checkbox"/> M	Electrical work <input type="checkbox"/> H <input type="checkbox"/> M	crance/lifting work <input type="checkbox"/> H <input type="checkbox"/> M	demolition work <input type="checkbox"/> yes	gas testing protocol <input type="checkbox"/> yes
work w. risk of falling <input type="checkbox"/> H <input type="checkbox"/> M	excavation work <input type="checkbox"/> H <input type="checkbox"/> M	asbestos works <input type="checkbox"/> H <input type="checkbox"/> M	disconnecting gas systems <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> H <input type="checkbox"/> M	drilling/probing work <input type="checkbox"/> yes	scaffolding permit <input type="checkbox"/> yes
minimum PPE:			Cordoning off the work area: - Outside: site fence (min. height 1m) or equivalent - Indoors: suitable barrier according to the situation		
Step No	hazards	Safety measures / additional PPE: see above		to use Tools/Documents ok?	
1	Preparation of the sampling area	Unauthorized people & disturbance of procedure through other people	Fencing & safety area		
2	Earthing	Spark due to electric charge	Avoiding of electric charge, light indicator		
3	Installation & sampling	Gas leak	Use of detectors/gas sensors or leak detection spray, Flushing procedure with N2		
4	H2 Venting	Combustion, explosion, pressure at the Vent	Safety area, safe standard procedure		
5	H2 detection – N2 flushing (or N2 leak)	Displacement of O2 in the trailer	Work outside, open doors for sufficient amount of time		
6	Filling & Venting	Exceeding operation limits of pressure sink	Temperature and pressure sensors		
7	Disconnecting after finishing	Pressure if not depressurized	4 eye policy		
The JHA only has to be checked and approved by the Permit Holder (PH) and Permit Issuer (PI) for high-risk work! →		responsible Executive (PH): JHA checked and adjusted if necessary	Issuer work permit (PI): JHA checked and proofed		
		name:	signature:	name:	signature:
Confirmation of the work team: Safety measures have been understood and are being observed					
name:	signature:	name:	signature:	name:	signature:
name:	signature:	name:	signature:	name:	signature:

Table 2. Onsite risk assessment for sampling/flow metering.

JHA - Job Hazard Analysis / Onsite risk assessment				Page 1/1							
The Predetermined JHA must be reviewed for the work that will occur EACH DAY that the permit is open! - Before and during work and in the event of changes: Observe the LMRA (Last Minute Risk Assessment)!											
Company:	JHA-No.:	Date:	Site-adress and -No.:								
To be executed task (s):											
Creator of JHA:											
Activities with high / medium risk (definition: see BBS activity table)			Special works:	More or other forms:							
hot work work w. risk of falling	<input type="checkbox"/> H <input type="checkbox"/> M	work in tight spaces excavation work	<input type="checkbox"/> H <input type="checkbox"/> M	Electrical work asbestos works	<input type="checkbox"/> H <input type="checkbox"/> M	crance/lifting work disconnecting gas systems	<input type="checkbox"/> H <input type="checkbox"/> M	demolition work drilling/probing work	yes <input type="checkbox"/> no <input type="checkbox"/>	gas testing protocol scaffolding permit	yes <input type="checkbox"/> no <input type="checkbox"/>
minimum PPE:		additional PPE necessary:		Cordoning off the work area: - Outside: site fence (min. height 1m) or equivalent - Indoors: suitable barrier according to the situation							
Step No	hazards	Safety measures / additional. PPE: see above			to use Tools/Documents	ok?					
1	Preparation of the sampling area	Unauthorized people & disturbance of procedure through other people	Fencing & safety area								
2	Earthing	Spark due to electric charge	Avoiding of electric charge, light indicator								
3	Installation & sampling	Gas leak	Use of detectors/gas sensors or leak detection spray, Flushing procedure with N2								
4	H2 Venting	Combustion, explosion, pressure at the Vent	Safety area, safe standard procedure								
5	H2 detection – N2 flushing (or N2 leak)	Displacement of O2 in the trailer	Work outside, open doors for sufficient amount of time								
6	Filling & Venting	Exceeding operation limits of pressure sink	Temperature and pressure sensors								
7	Disconnecting after finishing	Pressure if not depressurized	4 eye policy								
The JHA only has to be checked and approved by the Permit Holder (PH) and Permit Issuer (PI) for high-risk work! →		responsible Executive (PH): JHA checked and adjusted if necessary		Issuer work permit (PI): JHA checked and proofed							
name:		signature:		name:		signature:					
Confirmation of the work team: Safety measures have been understood and are being observed											
name:		signature:		name:		signature:					
name:		signature:		name:		signature:					

Table 3. Onsite risk assessment of parallel sampling of hydrogen fuel

JHA - Job Hazard Analysis / Onsite risk assessment				Page 1/2							
The Predetermined JHA must be reviewed for the work that will occur EACH DAY that the permit is open! - Before and during work and in the event of changes: Observe the LMRA (Last Minute Risk Assessment)!											
Company:	JHA-No.:	Date:	Site-adress and -No.:								
To be executed task (s): Sampling of hydrogen quality by using ENGIE system											
Creator of JHA:											
Activities with high / medium risk (definition: see BBS activity table)			Special works:	More or other forms:							
hot work work w. risk of falling	<input type="checkbox"/> H <input type="checkbox"/> M	work in tight spaces excavation work	<input type="checkbox"/> H <input type="checkbox"/> M	Electrical work asbestos works	<input type="checkbox"/> H <input type="checkbox"/> M	crance/lifting work disconnecting gas systems	<input type="checkbox"/> H <input type="checkbox"/> M	demolition work drilling/probing work	yes <input type="checkbox"/> no <input type="checkbox"/>	gas testing protocol scaffolding permit	yes <input type="checkbox"/> no <input type="checkbox"/>
minimum PPE:		additional PPE necessary:		Cordoning off the work area: - Outside: site fence (min. height 1m) or equivalent - Indoors: suitable barrier according to the situation							
Step No	hazards	Safety measures / additional. PPE: see above			to use Tools/Documents	ok?					
1	Preparation of the sampling area	Unauthorized people & disturbance of procedure through other people	Fencing & safety area								
2	Earthing	Spark due to electric charge	Avoiding of electric charge								
3	Installation & sampling	Gas leak	Use of detectors/gas sensors or leak detection spray								
4	Preparation of the analyzer with H2	Combustion, explosion, pressure	Safe by using standard procedure								
5	Inerting sampling lines and tank with N2	Gas leak, pressure, explosion	Work outside								
6	Flushing sampling lines with H2	Combustion, explosion, pressure	Safe by using standard procedure								
7	Start fueling and sampling	Combustion, explosion, pressure	Safe by using standard procedure								
8	Disconnecting after finishing	Pressure if not depressurized	4 eye policy								
The JHA only has to be checked and approved by the Permit Holder (PH) and Permit Issuer (PI) for high-risk work! →		responsible Executive (PH): JHA checked and adjusted if necessary		Issuer work permit (PI): JHA checked and proofed							
name:		signature:		name:		signature:					
Confirmation of the work team: Safety measures have been understood and are being observed											
name:		signature:		name:		signature:					
name:		signature:		name:		signature:					

Table 4. Onsite risk assessment of direct sampling of hydrogen

6.3 Onsite risk assessment of particulate sampling

Company:		JHA-No.:	Date:	Site-address and -No.:							
The Predetermined JHA must be reviewed for the work that will occur EACH DAY that the permit is open! - Before and during work and in the event of changes: Observe the LMRA (Last Minute Risk Assessment)!											
To be executed task (s):											
Creator of JHA:											
Activities with high / medium risk (definition: see BBS activity table)			Special works: More or other forms:								
hot work	<input type="checkbox"/> H <input type="checkbox"/> M	work in tight spaces	<input type="checkbox"/> H <input type="checkbox"/> M	Electrical work	<input type="checkbox"/> H <input type="checkbox"/> M	crance/lifting work	<input type="checkbox"/> H <input type="checkbox"/> M	demolition work	<input type="checkbox"/> yes	gas testing protocol	<input type="checkbox"/> yes
work w. risk of falling	<input type="checkbox"/>	excavation work	<input type="checkbox"/>	asbestos works	<input type="checkbox"/>	disconnecting gas systems	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	drilling/probing work	<input type="checkbox"/>	scaffolding permit	<input type="checkbox"/>
minimum PPE:			additional PPE necessary:			Conditioning off the work area:					
Step No			hazards			Safety measures / additional PPE: see above			to use Tools/Documents		
1	Preparation of the sampling area		Unauthorized people & disturbance of procedure through other people			Fencing & safety area					
2	Earthing		Spark due to electric charge			Avoiding of electric charge					
3	Assembly & sampling		Gas leak			Use of detectors/gas sensors or leak detection spray					
4	Venting of the system		Combustion, explosion			Operation done by trained personnel, safety area around the system					
5	Disconnecting after finishing		Pressure if not depressurized			4 eye policy					
The JHA only has to be checked and approved by the Permit Holder (PH) and Permit Issuer (PI) for high-risk work! →					responsible Executive (PH): JHA checked and adjusted if necessary			Issuer work permit (PI): JHA checked and proofed			
					name:			signature:			
					name:			signature:			
Confirmation of the work team: Safety measures have been understood and are being observed											
name:		signature:		name:		signature:		name:		signature:	
name:		signature:		name:		signature:		name:		signature:	

Table 5. Onsite risk assessment of particulate sampling in hydrogen

7 Conclusions

The good practice guide discusses first general aspect of venting and stresses out that venting requirements should be part of the sampling procedure. The document gives then guidelines for a safe venting during and after a sampling exercise focusing on ATEX zoning (general considerations and best practice during sampling exercises) and on the design of the venting stack.

The key points are to:

- Define the venting strategy for the sampling system and the targeted HRS type (i.e., mobile vent, connection to HRS vent, pressure, flow, ambient conditions as defined in section 3);
- Build venting systems appropriately for the system considering all specificity and sampling method associated as defined in section 4;
- The sampling system and vent should have defined ATEX category and ATEX zone during the different release scenario as defined in sections 5.3 and 5.4
- Develop a sampling methodology including equipment compliance, training, authorisation to work and risk assessment as defined in section 6

The development of hydrogen sampling and the enhancement of the sampling safety requires to further harmonise approaches. Further progress on the harmonisation of venting point at the HRS would support overall safer venting as portable vent may not be suitable in all situations (e.g., specific country regulation, HRS geometry, environment). Further research on hydrogen dispersion through vent would reduce ATEX area during sampling and may help reduce the amount of hydrogen released. The report describes the methodology to conduct risk assessments which are required before any sampling exercise, and examples are given at the end of the report. There is a variety of risk assessments methodologies and examples as highlighted in this document. To further strengthen the sampling safety, the use of quantitative risk assessments, lessons learned, good practice and robust practices (JHA, working permit) should be harmonised through the industry.

Such risk assessment harmonisation should improve safety and potentially help harmonising HRS safety across the industry.

Therefore, it is recommended to progress risk assessment harmonisation through future dedicated projects with HRS industry engagement and SDO involvement.

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